

ENHANCING TWO WHEELER SAFETY THROUGH EYE MONITORING HELMET TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract-- *In contemporary society, road safety is of paramount importance, especially for two-wheeler riders. This innovative solution to enhance rider safety by integrating an Infrared (IR) sensor-based eye blinked monitoring system into a helmet. The proposed system employs advanced sensor technology to detect the status of the rider's eyes, specifically monitoring whether they are open or closed. The system is the IR sensor strategically placed within the helmet to continuously monitor the rider's eye status. The IR sensor's data is processed using a microcontroller, which, upon detecting closed eyes, activates a compact vibration motor integrated into the helmet. Simultaneously, a buzzer is triggered to provide an audible warning to the rider. The power for the system is supplied by a Lithium Ion battery, known for its high energy density, compact size, and long cycle life, making it an ideal power source for wearable devices. The proposed intelligent helmet not only addresses the crucial issue of rider fatigue but also promotes a proactive approach to road safety. With a focus on addressing the unique challenges of long-duration rides, this project aims to provide a comprehensive solution that not only detects fatigue but actively alerts the rider, promoting heightened awareness and significantly advancing the safety paradigm for two-wheeler enthusiasts engaged in extended journeys. By leveraging modern sensor technologies and a reliable power source, this system aims to significantly reduce the likelihood of accidents caused by impaired alertness, ultimately contributing to a safer and more secure riding experience.*

Keywords : *IR sensor, buzzer, vibration motor, Arduino controller, eye blinking sensor.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of transportation, the safety of two-wheeler riders remains a critical concern. Accidents, often resulting from factors such as drowsiness and fatigue, pose significant threats to riders' well-being. Addressing this issue necessitates innovative solutions that seamlessly integrate with the rider's experience, enhancing safety without compromising comfort. This paper introduces an intelligent helmet equipped with an Infrared (IR) sensor-based eye monitoring system, designed to detect the status of the rider's eyes and provide timely alerts in case of potential drowsiness. The motivation behind this research stems from the alarming statistics related to two-wheeler accidents, with a considerable number attributed to impaired alertness.

Traditional safety measures, while effective to some extent, often lack the real-time monitoring capabilities required to address the dynamic nature of rider attention. This innovation is the IR sensor strategically incorporated into the helmet, constantly assessing whether the rider's eyes are open or closed. When closed eyes are detected, indicative of possible drowsiness or fatigue, the system responds by activating a vibration motor within the helmet and triggering a buzzer sound. This dual-alert mechanism is designed to capture the rider's attention promptly, alerting them to their compromised state and prompting a corrective response. To ensure the practicality and convenience of the system, a Lithium Ion battery serves as the power source. Renowned for its high energy density, compact form factor, and extended cycle life, the Lithium Ion battery enhances the helmet's usability and longevity, making it an ideal choice for a wearable safety device. We aim to address the specific safety concerns associated with long drives on two-wheelers, providing riders with an intelligent and responsive safety solution that actively promotes vigilance and well-being during extended periods of travel.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

TITLE: Accident Avoidance System Using Ir Sensors

AUTHOR: S.U.Nirumal Kumar, S.Niranjan, S.Mohamed Ismail

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DESCRIPTION: The unavailability of assistive technology, guidance system and the lethargic activities of the drivers has caused a number of accidents over the past few years. The accidents can be controlled by the implementation of the technology from the field of pneumatics and mechatronics. To avoid accidents and to prevent collisions we propose "Accident avoidance system by using IR sensors". The system works by using the inputs from the IR sensors. It detects if the driver has fallen asleep by observing the eye blinks and sends pulses via the microcontroller. This activates the alarm and hazard lamps as the first level of safety. If the driver is still asleep the seat starts to vibrate. Eventually, the pneumatic bumper and braking unit gets activated and halts the vehicle. At this point the driver must have regained his senses, the automatic steering control is provided that turns the vehicle in the direction away from the hindrance and avoids collisions. This system is aimed to provide safety to the passengers and avoid accidents by detecting lethargic driving activity

III. EMPATHY

Drowsiness and fatigue of the drivers are the main causes of accidents in the world. 21 percent of all fatal accidents are due to drowsy driving, late insights approximately assess that yearly 1,200 deaths and 76,000 wounds can be credited to exhaustion related mishaps. In 2017, 50,000 people were injured in drowsy driving accidents and 795 of those were killed because of drowsy driving. From 2009 to 2013, 72,000 police-reported motor vehicle accidents involving drowsy drivers. 39.2% identified that drowsy driving as "being unable to keep your eyes open" due to tiredness. The majority of respondents (64.4%) believe that drowsy driving is just as dangerous as texting while driving. Drowsiness can occur due to the tiredness and lack of sleep while driving. The best way to avoid accidents caused by drowsiness is to detect it and warn the driver before falling asleep.

IV. OBJECTIVE

The primary objective of implementing eye monitoring helmet technology in two-wheelers is to significantly enhance rider safety by addressing the critical issue of attentiveness. Utilizing an infrared (IR) sensor to detect eye blinking patterns, the system aims to distinguish between open and closed states of the rider's eyes. The key focus is to promptly identify signs of drowsiness or fatigue. Upon detection, the system activates a dual-alert mechanism, comprising an audible alert through a buzzer and a tactile alert via a vibration motor integrated into the helmet. The overarching goal is to alert the rider in real-time, mitigating the risk of accidents caused by reduced attentiveness during two-wheeler journeys. Powered by efficient Lithium Ion batteries and controlled by an Arduino Uno microcontroller, the technology seeks to provide a reliable, user-friendly, and proactive solution to significantly enhance the safety of riders on the road.

V. PREVIOUS RESEARCH WORK

In the existing sleep monitoring and alert system for a vehicle, the system employs a PIC microcontroller along with IR and ultrasonic sensors. The PIC microcontroller serves as the central processing unit, overseeing the real-time monitoring of the driver's state. The DDS operates without impeding the driver's experience, offering a comprehensive safety net that respects individual privacy. Furthermore, the system allows for customizable alert settings, recognizing the diverse nature of drivers and their preferences.

Its proven efficacy in preventing accidents related to driver drowsiness underscores its significance in the ongoing efforts to create a safer and more secure driving environment. The amalgamation of sensors, a buzzer, and a vibration motor in the DDS exemplifies a paradigm shift towards intelligent and proactive safety measures in the automotive landscape. This alert is conveyed through a combination of visual and audible signals, ensuring the driver is promptly notified and prompted to take corrective action, thereby enhancing safety during travel.

VI. COMPONENTS REQUIRED

- EYE BLINKING SENSOR
- LITHIUM-ION BATTERY
- BUZZER
- VIBRATION MOTOR
- ARDUINO UNO

VII. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure.1 Enhancing two wheeler safety through eye monitoring helmet technology

VIII. WORKING PRINCIPLE

To enhance the two-wheeler safety during long drives introduces a state-of-the-art eye monitoring helmet technology designed to mitigate the risks associated. The involves the integration of an infrared (IR) sensor within a helmet for real-time monitoring of the driver's eye blinks. This sensor continuously tracks the eye movements, and when it detects prolonged eye closure indicative of drowsiness or distraction, the system responds with a dual-alert mechanism. In the vibration motor embedded in the helmet is activated to provide a physical alert to the driver, ensuring immediate attention. Simultaneously, a buzzer generates an audible warning, enhancing the effectiveness of the alert system. To ensure the reliability and portability of the system, a Lithium Ion battery serves as the primary power source. Lithium Ion batteries are chosen for their high energy density, compact form factor, and extended cycle life, making them well-suited for the confined space of a helmet while providing a sustainable and long-lasting power supply. This battery technology not only facilitates the seamless integration of the alert system but also aligns with the need for a robust and efficient power solution for on-the-go applications. In proposed system combines advanced sensing technology through an IR

sensor with a dual-alert mechanism comprising a vibration motor and a buzzer. The utilization of a Lithium Ion battery enhances the overall reliability and practicality of the system, offering a comprehensive solution for addressing the critical issue of drowsy driving and improving overall road safety.

IR Sensor:

- An infrared sensor is strategically placed within the helmet to monitor the driver's eye movements.
- The sensor continuously analyses the frequency and duration of eye blinks.

Vibration Motor:

- A compact vibration motor is embedded in the helmet.
- Activated upon detection of prolonged eye closure to physically alert the driver.

Buzzer:

- An audible warning system in the form of a buzzer is integrated.
- Sounds an alert in conjunction with the vibration motor to ensure the driver is promptly notified.

Lithium Ion Battery:

- The entire system is powered by a reliable and rechargeable Lithium Ion battery.
- Lithium Ion batteries provide high energy density, longevity, and a lightweight design, making them suitable for portable applications.

IX. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Figure.2 Circuit Diagram

X. TEST AND RESULT

XI. FUTURE SCOPE

In the advanced artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms could enhance the system's ability to analyze and interpret subtle eye movement patterns. This could lead to more accurate detection of drowsiness and early signs of distraction, improving the system's overall effectiveness.

Future developments might involve integrating the eye monitoring technology with the motorcycles on board systems. This could enable the helmet to communicate with the vehicle, automatically adjusting speed or triggering safety features in response to detected fatigue, creating a more interconnected safety ecosystem.

XII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Intelligent Helmet with Eye Blink Monitoring System represents a significant advancement in the realm of driver safety technology. In the infrared sensor to monitor eye blinks and subsequently activating a vibration motor and buzzer when signs of drowsiness are detected, the system provides a multi-sensory alert mechanism that aims to prevent accidents caused by driver fatigue. The integration of a Lithium Ion battery as the power source ensures a reliable and long-lasting energy supply, making the system practical for real-world applications. This proposed system not only addresses the immediate safety concern of drowsy driving but

also exemplifies a proactive approach towards enhancing road safety. The combination of innovative sensor technology and an efficient power solution contributes to a comprehensive and user-friendly design, aligning with the evolving needs of modern transportation. As the prevalence of smart technologies in vehicles continues to rise, the Intelligent Helmet with Eye Blink Monitoring System stands out as a promising solution to mitigate the risks associated with driver distraction and fatigue, ultimately fostering safer roads for all.

XIII. REFERENCE

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